

Synthesis and Thermolysis of Possible Laser Material—Part I

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Substituted ortho-hydroxy chalcones and acetophenone have been used as a co-ordinating ligand. The complex compounds of the ligands with Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) have been isolated and characterized on the basis of elemental analyses and from the thermolysis.

LASER technology as a unique tool has enticed the scientist of prevailing era to explore new laser material^{1,2}. The efficiency of chalcones³⁻⁷ ($\text{Ar}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{Ar}'$), and acetophenones⁸⁻¹¹ ($\text{Ar}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), have captivated us to synthesise the new laser material as reported by Charles^{1,2}, Patel^{1,3} and Garg^{1,4}. The chalcones have been prepared and have been introduced for the first time in the literature for the complexation of Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III). An idea smote to prepare the complexes of these metal ions with 2-hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone, 2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl chalcone, 2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl-5'-chloro chalcone, 2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro chalcone and 2'-hydroxy-5'-bromo chalcone. The present manuscript is a part of our comprehensive study during the investigation of these complexes as laser material.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-bromo acetophenone (HBA); m.p. 62°, was prepared as Noris and Sturgies¹⁵ and 2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl chalcone (HMC); m.p. 88.5°, 2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl-5'-chloro chalcone (HMCC); m.p. 141°, 2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro chalcone (HCC); m.p. 108° and 2'-hydroxy-5'-bromo chalcone (HBC); m.p. 107-8° were prepared by the method of Kerrer *et al*¹⁶.

The solutions of rare earth chlorides of AnalaR grade and ligands were prepared in ethanol. The thermogravimetric data have been recorded by programming the furnace temperature at the rate of 5° per minute and thermograms were plotted between temperature and percentage of weight loss of the complexes.

Preparation of Complexes :

To a solution of 0.005 mole of rare earth chloride, the 0.017 mole of ligand solution was added with vigo-

rous stirring. On addition of 1 : 20 (water : ammonia) mixture, the precipitation of Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) complexes were obtained. The complexes were washed with hot ethanol-water mixture and then dried in an oven at 110°.

The percentage of metal in the complex was determined by heating and igniting the complex to its oxide. The oxide was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and titrated against EDTA using xynol orange indicator at pH 6 to find out the metal content.

The characteristic data of aforesaid complexes are tabulated in the Table 1.

Result and Discussion

The elemental analysis of the complexes correspond with the stoichiometry 1 : 3 between metal and ligand in each complex. These complexes are non-electrolytic in nature and show the inert behaviour towards all common organic solvents.

Thermolysis of Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) complexes with HBA :

The typical thermogravimetric curves (Fig. 1) for the samples of the $\text{Ln}(\text{HBA})_3$; $\text{Ln}=\text{Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III)}$ system show the rapid decomposition in the region 200-400°. This is in agreement with the reported work on the rare earth acetoacetonilide¹⁷. The order of decreasing heat stability was $\text{Y(III)} > \text{La(III)} > \text{Pr(III)} > \text{Nd(III)}$. The carbonaceous residue which remains unchanged at 740° contains all the metal initially present in the complexes, suggesting non-volatilization of the chelates under the experimental conditions. Weight loss above 400° can only be due to the pyrolysis of the initially formed decomposition products. Weight loss below 200° most likely represent

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS—RARE EARTH CHELATES

Complex	Colour	Elemental Analyses %					
		Carbon		Hydrogen		Metal	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Y(III)-HBA	Greenish Yellow	39.18	39.40	2.40	2.46	12.30	12.16
La(III)-HBA	"	36.84	36.87	2.28	2.30	18.00	17.78
Pr(III)-HBA	"	36.84	36.78	2.48	2.29	18.28	17.99
Nd(III)-HBA	"	36.70	36.62	2.28	2.28	18.48	18.34
La(III)-HMC	Yellow	67.72	67.77	4.70	4.58	16.17	16.34
La(III)-HMCC	Orange-Yellow	60.70	60.41	3.49	3.77	14.29	14.57
La(III)-HCC	" "	58.98	59.24	3.48	3.29	15.41	15.24
La(III)-HBC	" "	51.58	51.67	2.93	2.87	13.33	13.29

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

either slow decomposition or the loss of small amount of adhered ligand. The weight of metals calculated from the weight of the oxides (Y_2O_3 , La_2O_3 , Pr_2O_3 and Nd_2O_3) remaining when the residue from the thermogravimetric runs were reheated to 750° or above, also confirms the stoichiometric composition of $Ln(HBA)_3$. Since it is very difficult to precipitate these metals with HBA quantitatively, therefore, the thermogravimetric estimation can not be recommended for determining the lanthanones.

Thermolysis of La(III) complexes with chalcones :

The lanthanum complexes with chalcones viz., HMC, HMCC, HCC and HBC, were put for TGA to decide the effect of ligand on the nature of thermograms. The rapid decomposition in the region $200-400^\circ$ is also shown by the pyrolysis curve (Fig. 2) of these complexes.. The thermal stability of lanthanum

complexes is inversely proportional to their conversion factors (metal/metal-complex) as given in Table 2 because it is observed that the order of heat stability is $La(III)-HBC (160^\circ) > La(III)-HMCC (155^\circ) > La(III)-HCC (145^\circ) > La(III)-HMC (140^\circ)$; and the conversion factors are 0.1329, 0.1457, 0.1524 and 0.1634 for the corresponding complex i.e., higher the molecular weight of the reagent, the higher is the thermal stability of lanthanum chelate.

The above results coincide with the established facts that an increase in conjugation¹⁸ and an addition of extra aromatic ring¹⁹ in ligand enhance the thermal stability of its chelate resulting in an increase of electron density at reactive centres²⁰. The chalcone possesses $\alpha : \beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl group in the conjugation of two benzene rings and consequently increases the heat stability of its metal chelate to a great extent.

TABLE 2—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS DATA

Complex	Weight of sample taken mg.	Thermal stability Temp. (°C)	Decomposition Temp. (°C)	Approx. temp. (°C)	Possible residue	Residue %		Conversion Factor (Metal/Metal complex)
						Found	Calcd.	
Y(III)-HBA	85.0	165	280	760	Y ₂ O ₃	31.76	30.89	0.1216
La(III)-HBA	180.0	160	260	750	La ₂ O ₃	41.66	41.72	0.1778
Pr(III)-HBA	194.0	145	280	760	Pr ₂ O ₃	41.75	42.12	0.1799
Nd(III)-HBA	299.0	140	240	840	Nd ₂ O ₃	43.44	42.88	0.1834
La(III)-HMC	57.0	140	280	700	La ₂ O ₃	38.59	38.33	0.1634
La(III)-HMCC	34.0	155	320	740	„ „	32.35	43.17	0.1457
La(III)-HCC	32.0	145	260	740	„ „	34.37	35.75	0.1524
La(III)-HBC	31.0	160	240	840	„ „	32.25	31.18	0.1329

The data from pyrolysis curves are compiled in Table 2 which conspicuously indicate about the decomposition temperature and final product (expected) left after ignition.

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